

rity of analytical samples was checked by TLC. ^1H NMR spectra (90 MHz) were recorded in CCl_4 on EM 360/390 NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard (Chemical shifts in δ , ppm), IR spectra (thin film) were recorded on a Parkin-Elmer 337 IR spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}).

(3-*N,N*-Diethylamino-2-hydroxypropyl)-3-phenyl propenoate (**4a**): 3-Phenylpropenoic acid (4.4 g, 0.03 mol), anhydrous K_2CO_3 (7.62 g) and epichlorohydrin (85 ml, 1.08 mol) were refluxed under stirring for 13 h. The reaction mixture was filtered, the filtrate was concentrated and the residue was extracted in benzene. The organic phase was washed successively with 10% NaOH, water, saturated aqueous NaCl, dried and concentrated to afford a mixture of **2a**⁶ and **3a**⁷, as evident from its TLC (two spots).

The above mixture (**2a** and **3a**) (1.8 g) and diethylamine (3 g) was refluxed in absolute alcohol (25 ml) for one hour, cooled and alcohol was distilled off. The residue oil thus obtained was distilled under reduced pressure to give **4a**, yield 0.57 g (42%), b.p. 105–107°/6–8 mm; ν_{max} 3354, 1710, 1638 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.26 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.57 (6H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.75 (3H, m, $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})$), 5.35 (1H, d, J 17 Hz, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}$), 6.4 (1H, d, J 17 Hz, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}$), 7.50 (5H, m, Ar-H).

Compounds **4b-d** were prepared similarly from 3-(3-nitrophenyl)propenoic acid, 3-(4-chlorophenyl)propenoic acid, 3-(3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)propenoic acid respectively: **4b** (1.1 g, 50%), b.p. 112–114°/8–9 mm; ν_{max} (neat) 3356, 1712, 1643 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.1 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.5 (6H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.22 (1H, CHOH), 3.72 (1H, m, CHOH), 4.3 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, OCH_2CHOH), 5.40 (1H, d, J 17 Hz, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}$), 6.57 (1H, d, J 17 Hz, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}$), 7.69–8.5 (5H, m, Ar-H); **4c** (0.52 g, 40%) b.p. 115–117°/7–8 mm; ν_{max} (neat) 3396, 1716, 1639 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.08 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $-\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.60 (6H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.60 (3H, m, OCH_2CHOH), 5.30 (1H, d, J 17 Hz, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}$), 6.35 (1H, d, J 17 Hz,

$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}$), 7.45 (5H, m, Ar-H); **4d** (0.53 g, 45%), b.p. 110–112°/5–6 mm; ν_{max} (neat) 3360, 1704, 1624 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.05 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.35 (6H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.15 (1H, CHOH), 3.8 (12H, m, $(\text{OCH}_3)_3$, $\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})$), 5.35 (1H, d, J 17 Hz, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}$), 6.60 (1H, d, J 17 Hz, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CHCOO}$), 7.06 (2H, s, Ar-H).

Quaternary salts. General procedure :

A mixture of tertiary amine **4** (0.001 mol) dissolved in dry acetone (2.5 ml) and iodobutane (0.002 mol) was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. Removal of acetone afforded quaternary salts of ammonia as thick oil (yields 82–92%).

Biological evaluation :

Quaternary salts of ammonia were tested on hypocotyl cuttings of *Vigna radiata* (M.L. 207). Ten cuttings of mungbean (*V. radiata*) were taken in a vial to which 20 ml of test solution of different concentrations (5, 10, 15 and 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of different compounds had been poured. Each vial was kept at $28 \pm 2^\circ$ for 7 days and there after, the number of roots were recorded. Separate control treatments with ABA (5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and water were also performed simultaneously.

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